

The Result

a sustainable,
high-performance adhesive
ready for industrial adoption

Expected Impacts

Environmental:

Cuts CO₂ emissions by up to 30% and reduces formaldehyde & VOC emissions.

Economic & Industrial:

Delivers TRL7 bio-based adhesives, scaling to over 1,000 tons within one-year post project.

Societal:

Enables affordable, sustainable furniture and healthier indoor air.

Long-Term Vision

(within 5 years post project):

Supports industrial production of over 10,000 tons of bio-based adhesives annually for wood-based panel applications.

www.SUSBOARD.eu

Consortium

Coordinator:

RTDS Group

susboard@rtds-group.com

Scientific Coordinator:

Wood K plus

e.herwijnen@wood-kplus.at

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CBE JU. Neither the European Union nor the CBE JU can be held responsible for them.
Grant agreement ID: 101213812

© Sonae Auraco, Shutterstock
Layout & content: RTDS Association

www.SUSBOARD.eu

SUSBOARD

TOWARDS
100% BIO-BASED ADHESIVES
FOR SUSTAINABLE FURNITURE

www.SUSBOARD.eu

The Challenge

Conventional wood-based panels such as particleboard and MDF rely on fossil-based adhesives comprising formaldehyde. The wood panel industry urgently needs sustainable, high-performance alternatives that reduce environmental impact without compromising quality or cost.

SUSBOARD

Objectives

Replace traditional fossil-based adhesives with 100% bio-based alternatives.

Develop and scale up a formaldehyde-free, bio-based adhesive for wood panels.

Enhance the sustainability of wood furniture without compromising on durability.

Lower carbon footprint of the wood panel industry by up to 30%.

SUSBOARD Innovation

SUSBOARD develops and demonstrates 100% bio-based adhesive for industrial wood panel production.

Using a bio-based polymer derived from renewable sources, SUSBOARD replaces fossil-based resins.

